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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Rakhimov Matlab Farkhodovich PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORT AS A SOCIAL PHENOMENON.....	4
2. Қодирова Мадинабону Тургуновна ОТМ АРАБ ТИЛИ ЎҚИТУВЧИСИ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯСИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК-ПСИХОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ВА ИЖТИМОЙ ШАРТ- ШАРОИТЛАРИ.....	7
3. Asilova G.A. O‘ZBEK TILI TA‘LIMIDA FONETIK VA LEKSIK KO‘NIKMALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH (A1 daraja).....	17
4. Nazarova L. PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FACTORS IN FLIPPED CLASSES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING FOR ADULTS.....	23
5. Turg‘unboyev Sirojiddin Faxriddinovich OILAVIY BOLALAR UYI TARBIYALLANUVCHILARIDA KITOB O‘QISH MADANIYATINI SHAKLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI.....	28
6. Rejаметова Irada Ikramshikovna, Norbutayev Samandar Abdubakirovich YETIM VA OТА-ONA QARAMOG‘IDAN MAHRUM BO‘LGAN BOLALARDA IJTIMOIY KOMPETENTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	33
7. Хажиева И.А. АКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ, КАК СРЕДСТВО РАЗВИТИЯ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗОВ.....	38
8. Гизатулина Ольга Ивановна МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ СМЕШАННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ В ВУЗАХ.....	43
9. Носиров Рашод Адилевич, Рахимова Машхура Иномжановна, Темирова Светлана Владимировна ЖАМИЯТДА ИЖТИМОЙ ОНГНИНГ ЎЗГАРИШИ - ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАР ТАХЛИЛИ.....	51
10. Зарипова Д. А. ТАЪЛИМНИ АХБОРОТЛАШТИРИШДА ТАЛАБАЛАРНИ ИННОВАЦИОН ФАОЛИЯТНИ SMART УСУЛИ АСОСИДА ЎҚИТИШ МЕТОДИКАСИНИ АҲАМИЯТИ.....	58

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L. NazarovaTurin Polytechnic University in Tashkent
“Humanitarian and economic disciplines”**PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FACTORS IN FLIPPED CLASSES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING FOR ADULTS**

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ABSTRACT

Psycholinguistic factors in the form of motivation, foreign language anxiety, and self-confidence, affect adult EFL learners' learning process in a major way, positively or negatively. Many research studies done so far have shown that in a conventional classroom setup psycholinguistic factors affect the learning process of a large number of adult EFL learners negatively, because their motivation and self-confidence are low, while their foreign language anxiety is high. The objective of this paper is to describe of impact of psycholinguistic factors on the language learning process of students learning English through an unconventional pedagogic approach, that is, Flipped Classroom Model and how this model can assist to overcome this barriers.

Keywords: foreign language anxiety; motivation; self-confidence; Flipped Classroom; conventional classroom.

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ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИК ОМИЛЛАР****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Инглиз тилини хорижий тил сифатида ўқитиш жараёнига мотивация, ўзига бўлган ишонч ва хорижий тил ўрганишдаги ташвиш кўринишдаги психолингвистик омиллар ижобий ёки салбий таъсир кўрсатиши мумкин. Шу пайтгача қилинган тадқиқотлар катталарга хорижий тил ўқитишнинг анъанавий дарс жараёнларида психолингвистик: тил ўрганувчиларининг мотивацияси ва ўзига бўлган ишончи паст, лекин хорижий тил ўрганиш ташвишланиши эса юқори каби омиллар салбий таъсир қилаётганлигини кўрсатиб келмоқда. Ушбу мақолада инглиз тилини ноанъанавий педагогик ёндашув, флип таълим услуги орқали ўрганаётган талабаларнинг тил ўрганиш жараёнига психолингвистик омилларнинг таъсири ва шу услубнинг бу каби психолингвистик тўсқинларни енгиб ўтишга қанчалик фойдали эканлиги ҳақида ёзилган.

Калит сўзлар: ҳорижий тил ўрганишдаги ташвиш, мотивация, узига ишонч, Флип таълим услуби, анъанавий дарс жараёни.

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ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ В ФЛИП ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА ВЗРОСЛЫМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Психолингвистические факторы в виде мотивации, беспокойства по поводу иностранного языка и уверенности в себе в значительной степени влияют на процесс обучения взрослых, изучающих английский как иностранный, как положительно, так и отрицательно. Многие исследования, проведенные до сих пор, показали, что в обычном классе психолингвистические факторы негативно влияют на процесс обучения большому числу взрослых, изучающих английский язык, поскольку их мотивация и уверенность в себе низки, а их тревожность перед иностранным языком высока. Целью данной статьи является описание влияния психолингвистических факторов на процесс изучения языка учащимися, изучающими английский язык с помощью нетрадиционного педагогического подхода - модели Флип обучения, и того, как эта модель может помочь преодолеть эти барьеры.

Ключевые слова: тревожность в изучении иностранного языка, мотивация, самоуверенность, Флип обучение, традиционный класс.

Introduction.

Affective filter is a form of psycholinguistic factors such as motivation, foreign language anxiety, and self-confidence, can affect foreign language acquisition in a positive or negative way. These factors acquire the proportions of ‘barriers’ to language learning if they affect the learning process negatively. The sources and origin points of psycholinguistic barriers can be traced to multiple factors, and accordingly, they fall into numerous categories and affect learners in varying degrees, but the three factors that were chosen for investigation in the present study, i.e., anxiety, motivation, and self-confidence, are of most common occurrence, and negatively affecting a large number of foreign/second language learners [3] [6][8], although it is also interesting to note that learning a foreign language does not lead to anxiety of adults, rather, it helps them in their psychological well-being [7]. The effects of psycholinguistic factors on the performance of EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learners have been studied so widely and in such a wide variety of contexts in conventional, teacher-centered language classrooms that it would be impractical to cite only a few references in this regard, and it would suffice to mention that almost all of those studies have reported a negative impact of psycholinguistic factors on EFL learners’ language acquisition and proficiency development [5] [9]. However, later, owing to technological interventions in the class, there have been tremendous transformations in pedagogic practices. Flipped Classroom Model (FCM) as an approach to teaching, a learner-centered approach that relies heavily on information technology, multimedia, cyber gadgets, and virtual reality, has come into vogue in foreign language teaching classroom too and has largely proved successful in enhancing EFL learners’ learning experience in theory as well as in practice.

Data Analyses.

Affective factors play a crucial role in second language acquisition [8]. These are motivation, self-confidence, foreign language anxiety, and learners’ personality traits. The idea is that under the negative influence of affective states, some foreign language learners tend to filter out the input provided by the teacher in class. The effect of this affectation may be positive or negative on their learning process. Since the affecting factors commonly relate to the mental state of the learner, they are termed as psycholinguistic factors. If learners’ motivation and self-confidence to acquire language skills are low, while their anxiety towards learning is high, the learners will perform poorly in the

language, whereas, if their motivation and self-confidence levels are high and anxiety is low, they perform better in mastering the language skills. The factors are regarded as ‘barriers’ in this section since the studies referred to have studied only the negative effect of the factors on EFL learners’ learning process, i.e., the focus of all the research works was on investigating how adult EFL learners’ lack of motivation and self-confidence and high anxiety towards English affect their learning progress.

Psychological barriers are dispositional barriers since they arise from the mental disposition of learners. That is to say, if the mental state of learners predisposes them towards some task negatively, and thus prevents them from approaching the task with a positive frame of mind, the situation gives rise to psychological barriers. In language learning, a psychological barrier is the state of learners’ minds preventing them from learning a language properly, and so, it is termed as ‘psycholinguistic barrier’. Language learners facing psycholinguistic barriers may find language learning so challenging that they might give up all efforts to learn it. Researchers recognize four main psycholinguistic barriers to language learning, namely, low self-image, anxiety, lack of motivation, and wrong attitude towards the language. [2; 10].

Psycholinguistic barriers may be caused or affected by several factors. For instance, anxiety may be caused by fear of ridicule, peer-group influence or performance phobia, etc. Anxiety may aggravate because of the alien syntax, sounds, morphological elements, and semantic structure of the target language. Self-confidence may be low because of a low grasp of the fundamentals of the language. Motivation (intrinsic/extrinsic) may be lacking for learners’ visualization of the target language not of much use in the immediate contexts, and so on. Learners’ age and health are related to barriers to learning. Besides, mother-tongue influence, too, plays a big role in psychological barriers.

Motivation. EFL learners, especially, adult ones are demotivated due to their personal attitude towards learning language. As they start to learn a language in their adolescence, they do it for one specific purpose: for their job or any other necessity. They accept this process as mandatory and in most cases not a pleasant activity, because they cannot learn it as fast and easy as in their young ages. Moreover, this process goes difficult for them [4].

Self-confidence (also termed as ‘self-esteem’ or ‘self-efficacy’). It plays a significant role in foreign language learning, especially at the oral production stage. So many EFL learners lose confidence when faced with a sudden demand to converse with a fluent or native-like speaker of English. Self-confidence has been studied as a debilitating barrier [1] in research studies. Some adults are self-confident as they are afraid of making mistakes or to be ridiculous.

Anxiety. It is associated with the feeling of stress, tension, and worry. It may generate bodily changes, such as increased blood pressure and muscular tension. An ever-present anxiety is diagnosed as a personality disorder. Someone suffering from the disorder avoids situations causing anxiety. For example, a foreign language learner may develop a high level of foreign language anxiety, and as a result, would avoid using the language with others. Such a situation needs attention [8].

However, Flipped Classroom Model can be a good solution for taking out those psychological barriers [8]. FCL is a strongly learner-centered approach providing learners sufficient autonomy to choose their own time, pace, place, and supporting materials for the learning content. Keeping in view the positive impact of learner autonomy, it is considered that the autonomy gained by adult EFL learners, who are taught English using FCM as an approach, can have a positive impact on factors affecting their learning, such as motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety.

There are some key elements which can help adult students with the above psychological problems.

1. Providing an opportunity for students to gain first exposure prior to class for self-confidence and motivation.

The mechanism used for first exposure can vary, from simple textbook readings to lecture videos to podcasts or screencasts. Content can be created by the instructor or found online. The pre-class exposure doesn’t have to be high-tech; however students simply completed pre-class reading

assignments. Thus, learners can be aware of the material which is expected to be taught further, which can increase their self-confidence and motivation.

2. Providing an incentive for students to prepare for class for gaining self-confidence and motivation.

In FCM students complete a task associated with their preparation and that task is associated with points. The assignment can vary; there could be some tasks ranged from online quizzes to worksheets to short writing assignments, but in each case, the task provides an incentive for students to come to class prepared by speaking the common language of students: points. In many cases, grading for completion rather than effort can be sufficient, particularly if class activities provide students with the kind of feedback that grading for accuracy usually provides. So, students could be self-confident and motivated, that can decrease their anxiety during class time.

3. Providing a mechanism to assess student understanding for decreasing anxiety.

The pre-class assignments that students complete as evidence of their preparation can also help both the instructor and the student assess understanding. Pre-class online quizzes can allow the instructor to practice, which basically means that the instructor tailors class activities to focus on the elements with which students are struggling. If automatically graded, the quizzes can also help students pinpoint areas where they need help. Pre-class worksheets can also help focus student attention on areas with which they're struggling and can be a departure point for class activities, while pre-class writing assignments help students clarify their thinking about a subject, thereby producing richer in-class discussions. Importantly, much of the feedback students need is provided in class, reducing the need for instructors to provide extensive commentary outside of class. In addition, many of the activities used during class time can serve as informal checks of student understanding.

4. Providing in-class activities that focus on higher-level cognitive activities for self-confidence, motivation and working on anxiety.

If the students gained basic knowledge outside of class, then they need to spend class time to promote deeper learning. Again, the activity will depend on the learning goals of the class and the culture of the discipline. In other contexts, students may spend time in class engaged in debates, data analysis, or synthesis activities. The key is that students are using class time to deepen their understanding and increase their skills at using their new knowledge.

Conclusion

Initially, Flipped Class Models were created taking into consideration different type of learners with different type of psychological factors. So, the aim of this model is to involve learners, especially adult ones who are not confident, demotivated and anxious into learning before classes. The major psycholinguistic factors can influence adult EFL learners negatively or positively if they are taught English using FCM as an approach. It has a positive impact on adult EFL learners that should be employed as a language teaching approach with enough precautions to the point that students do not feel unnecessary burden the autonomy may put on them. Moreover, teachers using FCM should bear in mind that psycholinguistic barriers affect some learners even with a change in approach, and therefore, they need to adopt appropriate pedagogical techniques to ensure inclusiveness so that no students are left behind.

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